

ANC FOR $^{11}\text{B}+\text{p}\rightarrow^{12}\text{C}$ VERTEX FROM THE $^{11}\text{B}(^3\text{He},\text{d})^{12}\text{C}$ REACTION

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Abstract

The analysis of the differential cross section of the $^{11}\text{B}(^3\text{He},\text{d})^{12}\text{C}$ reaction measured at an incident energy of 10 MeV was performed within the framework of the modified distorted wave born approximation. The peripheral character of the reaction was tested. It was shown that, the considered reaction is peripheral at the main maximum of the angular distribution of the reaction under consideration. The squared ANC value for the $^{11}\text{B}+\text{p}\rightarrow^{12}\text{C}$ configuration was found to be $290.456\pm 20.105 \text{ fm}^{-1}$.

Key words

differential cross section, nuclear vertex constant, asymptotic normalization coefficient, radiative capture, peripheral reaction, spectroscopic factor

The DCS of the proton transfer reaction $^{11}\text{B}(^3\text{He},\text{d})^{12}\text{C}$ populating the ground state of ^{12}C was measured at a ^3He bombarding energy of 10 MeV [1] and the spectroscopic factor was extracted from the experimental data using DWBA calculation. We performed analysis of the DCS of the considered reaction. In the $^{12}\text{C}=\text{}^{11}\text{B}+\text{p}$ system, the transferred neutron has orbital momentum $l_{p^{11}\text{B}}=1$ for the ground state of ^{12}C and the corresponding total angular momentum is equal to $j_{p^{11}\text{B}}=3/2$. The orbital and total angular momenta of the transferred neutron in the $^3\text{He}=\text{d}+\text{p}$ system are equal to $l_{pd}=0$ and $j_{pd}=1/2$, respectively.

The calculation was performed using the LOLA code [2]. The ANC value for the $d+p \rightarrow {}^3\text{He}$ configuration was taken to be $4.28 \pm 0.5 \text{ fm}^{-1}$ from Ref. [3]. The parameter of OP for the entrance ${}^{11}\text{B}+{}^3\text{He}$ channel, labelled A1, was taken from Ref. [4]. The parameter of OPs for the exit ${}^{12}\text{C}+d$ channel was taken from Refs. [5-6] and it is labelled B1-B2.

By normalizing the calculated DCS within the framework of MDWBA to the experimental one at the forward angles $\theta < 20^\circ$, we extracted the values of the ANC for the ${}^{11}\text{B}+p \rightarrow {}^{12}\text{C}$ configuration. For each of the three experimental points of angles θ , the value of ANC for the ${}^{11}\text{B}+p \rightarrow {}^{12}\text{C}$ configuration is determined by using the central value $R(\theta, b_p {}^{11}\text{B}; 1 3/2)$ function, corresponding to the standard values of the parameters r_0 and a of the adopted W-S potential ($r_0=1.25 \text{ fm}$ and $a=0.65 \text{ fm}$).

Our recommended weighted average ANC value, obtained from OP set listed in Table 1, is $C_p^2 {}^{11}\text{B}; 1 3/2 = 290.456 \pm 20.105 \text{ fm}^{-1}$ for the ${}^{12}\text{C}$ nucleus ground state. The spectroscopic factor $Z_p {}^{11}\text{B}; 1 3/2$ of the ${}^{12}\text{C}$ nucleus in the (${}^{11}\text{B}+p$) channel is determined by the equation using the recommended ANC value in the present work and the value of single particle ANC $b_p {}^{11}\text{B}; 1 3/2$, corresponding to the standard values of the parameters r_0 and a of the adopted W-S potential ($r_0=1.25 \text{ fm}$ and $a=0.65 \text{ fm}$). The spectroscopic factor $Z_p {}^{11}\text{B}; 1 3/2$ of the ${}^{12}\text{C}$ nucleus in the (${}^{11}\text{B}+p$) channel are found to be $Z_p {}^{11}\text{B}; 1 3/2 = 2.855 \pm 0.198$ for the ${}^{12}\text{C}$ nucleus ground state.

Fig. 4. The DCS for the reaction $^{11}\text{B}(^3\text{He},d)^{12}\text{C}$ populating the ground (0^+ ; $E^*=0\text{MeV}$) state of the ^{12}C nucleus at an energy of 10 MeV. The experimental points are taken from [1]. The red and black solid lines are the calculated DCSs corresponding to set A1+B1 and A2+B2, respectively.

The calculated DCSs of the $^{11}\text{B}(^3\text{He},d)^{12}\text{C}$ reaction, populating the ground state of the ^{12}C nucleus, are presented in Fig.1 alongside the corresponding experimental data from reference [1]. The curve, which are shown in Fig. 1, represent calculations performed within the framework of the MDWBA, utilizing the weighted ANC value, across different OP sets. As demonstrated in the figure, the calculated DCSs within the framework of MDWBA exhibit good agreement with the experimental data, particularly within the main peak region of the angular distribution.

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